

THE LINGUOCULTUROLOGICAL PECULIARITIES OF SEMANTICAL EUPHEMISMS

Nasirdinov Oybek Abdubannonovich

a teacher of Kokand State Pedagogical Institute, Uzbekistan.

Email address: onasirdinov@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT: Stylistic devices as well as euphemisms are good way of expressing ideas. Moreover, euphemism can be used in literal texts. The aim of the article is to show some difficulties in translation and understanding of euphemisms linguoculturologically.

KEY WORDS: euphemism, linguoculturology, stylistic devices, culture, linguistics, relations with other styles.

The use of euphemisms can vary depending on the culture, society, and historical period in which they are used. The linguoculturological peculiarities of euphemisms refer to the specific ways in which language reflects the cultural and social context in which it is used. Euphemisms are a particularly interesting area of study because they often involve substituting a less direct or explicit term for a more taboo or sensitive one, and this process can reveal a great deal about the values, beliefs, and attitudes of a given culture or society. Here are some of the linguoculturological peculiarities of euphemisms:

1. Cultural taboos: Euphemisms are often used to express sensitive topics in a way that conforms to social and cultural norms. For example, in some cultures, euphemisms may be used to avoid discussing death or illness directly. The words and phrases used to describe these subjects can vary widely across cultures, and studying the euphemisms used in different languages and societies can help shed light on the ways in which these taboos are understood and managed.
2. Power relations: Euphemisms can also reveal power relations within a society, particularly with regard to issues of race, class, and gender. The words used to describe marginalized groups or individuals may be more euphemistic or derogatory, while those used to describe privileged groups may be more neutral or positive.
3. Historical context: Euphemisms can change over time, reflecting shifting cultural norms and values. For example, terms used to describe mental illness or disability may have evolved over the years as our understanding of these conditions has changed.
4. Regional differences: Euphemisms can also vary by region, reflecting regional dialects and cultural practices. For example, the words used to

describe alcoholic beverages may vary widely across different parts of the world, reflecting differences in local customs and traditions.

5. Creative expression: Finally, euphemisms can be seen as a form of creative expression, allowing individuals to play with language and explore new ways of expressing ideas. The use of euphemisms in literature and art can be particularly illuminating, revealing the unique linguistic and cultural perspectives of individual artists and writers.

When dealing with the definition of euphemisms, Abrantes differentiates between conventional and official euphemisms according to the degree of their lexicalization and the amount of knowledge needed for decoding their meaning. Burkhart (2010) additionally makes a distinction between veiling and concealing euphemisms in keeping with their role in the given context - be it not directly mentioning taboo topics, or deliberate hiding of truth. These subdivisions make it necessary to distinguish functions which euphemisms fulfill in various communicational situations.

Abrantes adds that owing to conventional euphemism being a response to social taboos, its function is to avoid being offensive. Official euphemism, on the other hand, "is deliberately used as a means of avoiding a negative reference, strategically motivated by political and military interests (e.g. not passing information to the opponent during the war or not damaging the image of politicians involved in it)".¹ Hence there exists the analogy with veiling and concealing types of euphemisms proposed by Burkhart.

When the speaker decides to use a euphemism in order to avoid being offensive, i.e. conventional euphemism, it is likely that the hearer recognizes this intention of his/her and verbally collaborates with the speaker. When the speaker chooses an official euphemism, the collaboration is destined to fail. Because the speaker is aware of the negativity of the subject and the effect it may cause on the hearer, the speaker decides not to mention it openly. The hearer cannot detect/decode the euphemism as it is effective in not to be

¹ Abrantes, Ana Margarida (2005) Euphemism and Co-operation in Discourse. In: Grillo, Eric (ed.) Power without Domination: Dialogism and the Empowering Property of Communication. Philadelphia, PA: John Benjamins Publishing Company, 88.

explicit. In this way, the hearer only receives the mental picture the speaker wants him/her to receive.²

Euphemistic words and phrases are caused in speech by moral and religious motives in order to disguise and cover up the terrible, shameful or odious sense of a statement. Socially negative and immoral behavior, which is likely to be discussed in modern civilized society through the use of more acceptable and decent communicative replacements. Phraseological units are an agreeable way to euphemize such cultural phenomena due to their indefinite semantics and cultural connotation, reproducibility and stability in speech. They are capable of producing a refining effect, referring communicants to a wide cultural context and joint memory of stereotype-based information. Phraseological euphemisms derive their semantics not only from the linguistic but also from the national and cultural background, which plays an important role in reevaluating phenomenon.

Euphemisms used every day are diverse and can be found in all kinds of communicative situations. Their usage is based on functions they fulfill in the given context.

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² Abrantes, Ana Margarida (2005) Euphemism and Co-operation in Discourse. In: Grillo, Eric (ed.) Power without Domination: Dialogism and the Empowering Property of Communication. Philadelphia, PA: John Benjamins Publishing Company, 85-103.

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